

H₂ FORM 3G

Exploring hydrogen effect on the formability of 3rd generation advanced high-strength steels for future vehicle designs

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Co-funded by
the European Union

The H2FORM3G project has received funding from the European Union's Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS): project num. 101157237. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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